

Three – Pass Fire Tube Boilers for production of Steam, Hot Water and Superheated Water

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Abstract

In this paper, the technical details and specifications of Three – Pass Fire Tube Boilers for production of Steam, Hot Water and Superheated Water, are introduced.

The most manufactured steam generator type for output flow rate capacities ranging from 1 t/h to 30 t/h is the three-pass fire tube boiler unit, fired by gas or oil and delivered in a pre-fabricated form.

Regarding the smaller or medium output ranges of saturated steam and hot water; saturated steam boiler, low pressure steam boiler, superheated steam boiler and hot water boiler variation models are manufactured. All models commonly must have the optimum production engineering and thermodynamical design specifications, the highest technically possible efficiency rate, easy to operate with low maintenance works, high quality and time-tested components for firing and control, modern manufacturing methods with corresponding high quality control, international supervision, classification, inspection and approval of an independent third party notified body as well as quality control and quality assurance activities to be realized by the independent quality department & organization of the boiler manufacturer company.

These three-pass fire tube boilers use fuel which is gas or oil and then produce heat energy, steam and power, respectively. As a general constructional structure, the pressurized boiler shell has end-shell plate, generous fire-tube dimensions for optimum combustion and lower emissions, optimum layout and dimensions of flue-gas passes, more steam space to obtain high quality steam, water cooled reversing chamber, large water volume.

The difference between the feed water and the exit flue gas temperature is the main source of energy. The three-pass fire tube boilers can achieve an average efficiency of 89%. This efficiency can be increased considerably by installing a feed water pre-heater (economizer) to take the advantage of temperature difference. In new boiler units economizers must always be included to the system.

Keywords: Three-Pass Fire Tube Boiler, Steam Generator, Steam, Hot Water, Superheated Water, Energy, Energy Efficiency, Energy Transfer, Heat Energy, Thermodynamics, Fluid Mechanics, Heat Transfer, Mathematics, Energy Production Systems.

INTRODUCTION

The most manufactured steam generator type for output flow rate capacities ranging from 1 t/h to 30 t/h is the three-pass fire tube boiler unit, fired by gas or oil and delivered in a pre-fabricated form. Hot water three-pass fire tube boilers are classified in two groups.

Low pressure hot water boilers have a maximum output temperature of 120 °C and are manufactured according to TRD 702 Standards. High pressure hot water boilers have output temperatures of above 120 °C and are also manufactured according to TRD 402 Standards.

Due to the large water volumes necessary in such units, these boilers have special pipe configuration and hot water supports which enable the return water to mix inside the boiler thoroughly.

Regarding the smaller or medium output ranges of saturated steam and hot water; saturated steam boiler, low pressure steam boiler, superheated steam boiler and hot water boiler variation models are manufactured. All models commonly must have the optimum production engineering and thermodynamical design specifications, the highest technically possible efficiency rate, easy to operate with low maintenance works, high quality and time-tested components for firing and control, modern manufacturing methods with corresponding high quality control, international supervision, classification, inspection and approval of an independent third party notified body as well as quality control and quality assurance activities to be realized by the independent quality department & organization of the boiler manufacturer company.

These three-pass fire tube boilers use fuel which is gas or oil and then produce heat energy, steam and power, respectively. As a general constructional structure, the pressurized boiler shell has end-shell plate, generous fire-tube dimensions for optimum combustion and lower emissions, optimum layout and dimensions of flue-gas passes, more steam space to obtain high quality steam, water cooled reversing chamber, large water volume. As the boiler material; the boiler body, dished ends, furnace and fire box according to DIN 17155, are made of 17 Mn 4 also known as P295 GH and/or HII quality special boiler steel, St 35.8-I quality seamless steel tubes are used for boiler tubes and these correspond to DIN 17175.

Boiler output, burner system and size determine the type of variant. Three pass system remains unchanged.

A superheater is installed to raise the steam temperature above that of the saturated steam. It is installed in the front reversing chamber if only low superheating is required. If higher temperatures are needed, it is installed in the inside or outside reversing chamber where a higher flue gas temperature is obtained. An economiser is added to the boiler exit for further utilization of the flue gas energy.

As the steam production; the boiler is fed with treated water. Guides installed in the water space ensure even distribution. The arrangement of the fire tube (furnace) and the flue gas smoke tubes guarantees uninterrupted development of steam bubbles and stable water circulation under all operating conditions. This is one of the basic prerequisites for a long service life of the boiler.

The steady and even admission of water to all tube banks and surrounding parts like the fire tube, flue gas tubes and reversing chambers guarantees highly efficient heat flux. Thus, the thermal stress is kept to a minimum.

The below diagram given by Figure 1 shows the temperature profile in the three-pass fire tube boiler for fuel-oil. [1]

Figure_1: The diagram of temperature profile in the three-pass fire tube boiler for fuel-oil. [1]

Method, Findings and Discussion

The three-pass fire tube boiler is primarily designed for gas (natural gas) or liquid fuel. Other than the burner additional special equipment is not needed either for oil or gas firing or for a combination of both. For heavy oil firing, local directives regarding emissions are taken into account. The below diagram given by Figure 2 shows a time, tested boiler model for combined firing. Pressurized or rotary atomizing burner are installed. The gas lines are constructed and laid out to ensure safety and absolute gas tightness.

Figure_2: The boiler model for combined firing. [1]

The numbered parts and sections on Figure 2 are explained as follows: [1]

1. Boiler
2. Combined oil and gas burner
3. Gas pressure regulating
4. Safety valve
5. Oil supply and return
6. Fuel-oil pre-heater
7. Oil-pump

It is legally permitted to operate a boiler without continuous supervision when special supervisory equipment has been installed. 24 hours and 72 hours periodic controls are accepted by German TRD 604 Standard. This additional equipment is shown in the below diagram given by Figure 3. [1] According to German TRD 603 Standard, periodic high and low pressure operation is also possible.

Figure_3: The diagram of special supervisory equipment required by German TRD 604 Standard. [1]

The numbered parts and items on Figure 3 are explained as follows: [1]

German TRD 604 / 24 hours:

- 1- Water level limiter “min”
- 2- 2nd water level limiter “min”
- 3- Limit switch to shut off boiler feed water pumps
- 4- Electrical conductivity limiter of boiler water
- 5- Limiter of superheated steam temperature

German TRD 604 / 72 hours:

- 6- Water level limiter “min”
- 7- Conductivity control + limitation (item 4 is cancelled)
- 8- Monitoring of conductivity and turbidity
- 9- Monitoring of fresh water hardness
- 10- Water level “min”
- 11- Safety valve in gas line
- 12- 2nd gas pressure monitor “min”
- 13- 2nd gas pressure monitor “max”
- 14- Gas tightness monitoring of main gas valve
- 15- 2nd gas ignition valve
- 16- Quick closing valve
- 17- Quick closing valve on oil return
- 18- Oil pressure monitor “min”
- 19- 2nd oil pressure monitor “min”
- 20- 2nd combustion air pressure switch
- 21- 2nd atomiser air pressure switch
- 22- Self-checking flame detector

The three-pass fire tube boiler for generation of saturated steam is shown in Figure 4, as below.

Figure_4: The three-pass fire tube boiler for generation of saturated steam. [1]

The numbered sections on Figure 4 are explained as follows: [1]

- 1- Boiler body
- 2- Furnace
- 3- Smoke tubes 2. Pass
- 4- Smoke tubes 3. Pass
- 5- Water cooled firebox
- 6- Front reversing chamber
- 7- Smoke outlet
- 8- Boiler frame
- 9- Insulation
- 10- Burning system gas or/and fuel-oil burner
- 11- Feed water pump(s)
- 12- Feed water valve
- 13- Steam valve
- 14- Safety valve
- 15- Water level limiter
- 16- Blow down valve
- 17- Water level indicator(s)
- 18- Pressure controller(s)
- 19- Pressure gauge(s)

The three-pass fire tube boiler for generation of high temperature hot water is shown in Figure 5, as below.

Figure_5: The three-pass fire tube boiler for generation of high temperature hot water. [1]

The numbered sections on Figure 5 are explained as follows: [1]

- 1- Boiler body
- 2- Furnace
- 3- Smoke tubes 2. Pass
- 4- Smoke tubes 3. Pass
- 5- Water cooled firebox
- 6- Front reversing chamber
- 7- Smoke outlet
- 8- Boiler frame
- 9- Insulation
- 10- Burning system gas or/and fuel-oil burner
- 11- Hot water outlet with armatures
- 12- Water return
- 13- Safety valve
- 14- Feed water inlet
- 15- Blow down valve

CONCLUSION

The numbered parts, items and also the general dimensions of the three-pass fire tube boiler for generation of saturated steam are shown in Figure 6, as below. [1]

The numbered parts, items and also the general dimensions of the three-pass fire tube boiler for generation of high temperature hot water are shown in Figure 7, as below. [1]

All the detailed technical specifications including boiler type, maximum permissible operating pressure, heating surface, water volume, transport weight, furnace type, fuel consumption, etc. and the boiler dimensions for generation of saturated steam is shown in Table 1, as below. [1]

All the detailed technical specifications including boiler type, maximum permissible operating pressure, heating surface, water volume, transport weight, furnace type, fuel consumption, etc. and the boiler dimensions for generation of high temperature hot water is shown in Table 2, as below. [1]

Figure 6_ The numbered parts, items and also the general dimensions of the three-pass fire tube boiler for generation of saturated steam. [1]

Figure_7: The numbered parts, items and also the general dimensions of the three-pass fire tube boiler for generation of high temperature hot water. [1]

		Çift kullanan : Double furnace																											
Tip Type	Maksimum çalışma basıncı Max. Permissible operation press	HD	8	12	16	18	22	30	40	52	65	80	100	125	140	165	200	240	280	300	305	335	370	410	460	500	540		
		bar	18	18	18	18	18	14	19	27	25	23	25	23	25	20	24	22	20	18	18	24	24	23	22	20	18	18	
Kapasite Rating	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	kg/h	260	400	650	800	1000	1250	1600	2100	2600	3200	4000	5000	6000	7000	8000	10000	11500	12500	14000	16000	19000	20000	23000	25000		
			kg/h	325	500	800	1000	1250	1600	2000	2600	3200	4000	5000	6000	7000	8000	10000	12000	14000	16000	19000	20000	22000	25000	28000	30000		
Isi Heat	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	MW	0,17	0,26	0,42	0,52	0,65	0,81	1,00	1,37	1,69	2,19	2,60	3,25	3,90	4,55	5,20	6,50	7,48	8,13	8,45	9,10	10,40	11,70	13,00	14,95	16,25	
			Gcal/h	0,15	0,22	0,36	0,45	0,56	0,70	0,86	1,10	1,37	1,79	2,24	2,80	3,35	3,91	4,47	5,59	6,43	7,27	7,83	8,94	10,06	11,18	12,86	13,98		
Isıtma yüzeyi Heating surface	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	MW	0,21	0,33	0,52	0,65	0,81	1,00	1,30	1,69	2,08	2,60	3,25	3,90	4,55	5,20	6,50	7,80	9,10	9,75	10,40	11,70	13,00	14,30	16,25	18,20	19,60	
			Gcal/h	0,18	0,28	0,45	0,56	0,70	0,86	1,12	1,45	1,79	2,24	2,80	3,35	3,91	4,47	5,59	6,71	7,83	8,39	8,94	10,06	11,18	12,30	13,98	15,65	16,77	
Su hacmi (dolu) Water volume (full)	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	m ³	8	12	15,5	18	22	29	39	52	65	80	100	127	140	165	200	240	280	300	305	335	370	410	460	500	540	
			m ³	0,76	0,98	1,13	1,40	1,72	2,18	3,42	4,80	6,00	7,60	9,80	12,60	13,40	15,10	19,40	22,80	24,10	25,70	31,30	33,60	36,60	41,80	45,40	46,80	49,00	
Taşıma ağırlığı Transport weight	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	t	1,90	2,40	2,80	3,30	4,00	4,80	5,90	7,30	8,60	10,30	12,20	15,20	16,80	18,30	21,20	25,00	26,90	28,20	31,40	33,40	35,80	39,40	43,50	48,10	50,40	
			kg/h	19	28	45	55	69	86	103	144	178	220	274	343	411	480	548	685	822	959	1028	1096	1233	1370	1508	1714	1918	2055
Doğalgaz Natural gas M ³ /h	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	Nm ³ /h	22	35	55	69	86	103	137	178	220	274	343	411	480	548	685	822	959	1028	1096	1233	1370	1508	1714	1918	2055	
			Nm ³ /h	27	40	65	80	100	127	160	207	256	320	400	478	558	638	798	957	1117	1197	1275	1435	1595	1754	1994	2232	2392	
Ölçüler (yaklaşık) Dimensions (app)	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	L mm	2540	2845	2785	2885	3125	3815	4560	4870	5740	6540	6150	7080	7870	7870	8590	8990	7435	7720	7920	8370	8420	8600	9250			
			B mm	1580	1700	1730	1680	1900	1995	2190	2280	2360	2460	2660	2680	2860	2960	3150	3260	3450	3450	3600	3600	4000	4100	4200	4400	4500	4500
Dumaneğin çıkış ölçüleri Smoke outlet dimensions	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	H mm	1880	2030	2080	2230	2290	2380	2540	2640	2810	2910	3165	3365	3500	3600	3800	4100	4200	4200	4515	4685	4795	4885	5225	5380		
			D mm	2050	2250	2300	2250	2500	2600	3000	3050	3050	3250	3350	3550	3650	3750	3900	4000	4200	4300	4300	4600	4600	4800	4900	5100	5200	5300
	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	D mm	1200	1350	1400	1500	1550	1600	1800	1900	2000	2100	2300	2500	2500	2600	2800	3000	3100	3100	3600	3700	3800	3900	4100	4200	4200	
			H mm	1590	1650	1700	1800	1850	1900	2100	2200	2300	2400	2600	2900	2900	3000	3400	3400	3400	3400	3700	3800	3880	3980	4280	4380	4580	
	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	D mm	200	200	250	300	300	300	400	400	500	500	600	600	700	700	800	800	900	900	1000	1000	1100	1100	1200	1300	1300	
			H mm	850	850	965	965	1035	1090	1280	1370	1390	1480	1600	1710	1770	1920	2110	2075	2075	2280	2480	2480	2790	2790	2950	2950	2850	
	Nominal Nominal	Sürekli maksimum Maximum continuous	B mm	300	320	365	390	390	430	430	520	530	570	620	675	675	670	750	810	850	850								

Table_1: Technical specifications including boiler type, maximum permissible operating pressure, heating surface, water volume, transport weight, furnace type, fuel consumption, etc. and the boiler dimensions for generation of saturated

steam. [1] (Note: 10 Bar(g) saturated steam, feed water temperature of 102 °C and maximum 12% excess air firing conditions)

		Çift Kılıhanlı; Double furnace																							
Tip Type	HW	8	12	16	18	22	30	40	52	65	80	100	125	140	155	175	200	230	260	285	320	370	405	440	500
Maksimum çalışma basıncı Max. Permissible operation press	bar	18	18	18	18	18	18	14	19	27	25	23	25	20	24	23	22	20	18	19	23	22	21	20	18
	MW	0,17	0,26	0,38	0,45	0,55	0,73	0,98	1,36	1,68	2,08	2,64	3,2	3,68	4,16	4,8	5,6	6,56	7,44	8,4	9,6	11,2	12,00	12,8	14,88
İsteme yüzeyi Heating surface	metrekare Rating	0,15	0,22	0,33	0,39	0,47	0,63	0,84	1,17	1,44	1,79	2,27	2,75	3,16	3,58	4,13	4,82	5,64	6,40	7,22	8,26	9,63	10,32	11,01	12,80
	Süreli maksimum Maximum continuous	MW	0,21	0,32	0,48	0,56	0,69	0,91	1,22	1,7	2,1	2,6	3,3	4,0	4,6	5,2	6,0	7,0	8,2	9,3	10,5	12,0	14,0	15,0	16,0
Su hacmi (dolu) Water volume (full)	metrekare Rating	0,18	0,27	0,41	0,48	0,59	0,78	1,05	1,46	1,64	2,23	2,84	3,44	3,96	4,47	5,16	6,02	7,05	8,00	9,03	10,32	12,04	12,9	13,76	16,00
	Süreli maksimum Maximum continuous	m ³	8	12	15,5	18	22	29	39	52	65	80	100	127	140	155	174	199	228	260	285	320	370	405	440
Taşıma ağırlığı Transport weight	kg	1,7	2,2	2,4	2,8	3,2	4,2	5,4	7,3	8,6	10,3	12,2	15,2	16,8	18,3	19,6	20,8	22,4	24,5	27,6	30,05	33,8	38,7	40,7	46,2
	Süreli maksimum Maximum continuous	kg	18	27	40	47	57	88	101	140	173	215	272	330	379	429	495	577	676	767	865	989	1153	1236	1319
Füaj ölçüleri Fuel connection Dimensions (app)	mm	25	38	58	67	83	109	148	204	229	311	396	480	552	623	719	839	963	1115	1258	1438	1678	1786	1918	2230
	Süreli maksimum Maximum continuous	mm	25	38	58	67	83	109	148	204	229	311	396	480	552	623	719	839	963	1115	1258	1438	1678	1786	1918
Duman gazı çıkış ölçüleri Smoke outlet dimensions	mm	250	320	365	390	430	480	530	570	620	670	720	770	820	870	920	970	1020	1070	1120	1170	1220	1270	1320	1370
	Süreli maksimum Maximum continuous	mm	250	320	365	390	430	480	530	570	620	670	720	770	820	870	920	970	1020	1070	1120	1170	1220	1270	1320

Table_2: Technical specifications including boiler type, maximum permissible operating pressure, heating surface, water volume, transport weight, furnace type, fuel consumption, etc. and the boiler dimensions for generation of high temperature hot water. [1] (Note: 10 Bar (g) operating pressure, 160 / 120 °C water outlet and return temperature and maximum 12% excess air firing conditions)

The difference between the feed water and the exit flue gas temperature is the main source of energy. The three-pass fire tube boilers can achieve an average efficiency of 89%. This efficiency can be increased considerably by installing a feed water pre-heater (economizer) to take the advantage of temperature difference. In new boiler units economizers must always be included to the system. In case of existing ones, adding an economizer can greatly improve the unit's efficiency. The economizer can be installed in various positions between the flue-gas outlet of the boiler and the stack. The most favorable route for the flue-gas must be applied. [1], [2], [3], [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16], [17], [18], [19]

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